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ON THE COMPLEMENTARITY OF GLOBAL HAGUE AND REGIONAL EUROPEAN UNION - UNIFICATION OF PRIVATE INTERNATIONAL LAW

A. Introduction – Unification of private international law by the Hague Conference and by the EU: two interconnected development paths

I am honoured and delighted to have been invited to take part in this anniversary conference, and grateful to Prof. Sanja Marjanovic and her colleagues, as well as Prof Crista Jessel Holst and the GIZ foundation, for making this conference – once again – possible!

What a great vision Professor Mirko Živkovic had, twenty years ago, to initiate these regional conferences on private international law! I have always admired these meetings as extraordinary opportunities to build bridges between scholars and practitioners of private international law from South-East Europe and, beyond, with other fellow European specialists in the field.

Since this is a jubilee conference, it is perhaps appropriate to refer to another international law conference jubilee. This year, the *Institut de droit international* commemorates 150 years since it was founded in 1873 by some of the most eminent jurists of the time, including Pasquale Mancini and Tobias Asser. Mancini and Asser were the driving forces behind the idea of a European codification of private international law, an idea which the *Institut* embraced, and started working on right away¹.

So, in a way the founding of the *Institut de droit international* in 1873 also marks the birth of European efforts to unify private international law.

¹ Session de Genève, 1874, Résolution sur l'Utilité d'un accord commun des règles uniformes de droit international privé, https://www.idi-iil.org/app/uploads/2017/06/1874_gen_01_fr.pdf.

Twenty years later, on Asser's initiative - inspired by Mancini, as he always stressed - the Dutch government convened a conference of European states on private international law. The Hague Conference of 1893 became the first of six conferences on private international law organized before the Second World War. But it would take until 1955 before the Hague Conference on Private International Law (Hague Conference, HCCH) became operational as a *permanent* intergovernmental organization.

Shortly afterwards, in 1958, the European Economic Community was created. As a follow-up to Article 220 of the Treaty of Rome establishing the EEC, the six original Member States agreed to negotiate an instrument to ensure "... the simplification of formalities, to which the reciprocal recognition and enforcement of judgments are subject ...". The result was the 1968 Brussels Convention, which was essentially intended for use *within* the Community, leaving relations with *third* countries to *national law*.²

The idea of a multilateral convention on the recognition and enforcement of judgments was in fact an old idea of Asser's, for which he was called *avisionnaire*, a visionary of the Brussels Convention.³ Asser had already passed away when the 1925 Hague Conference adopted a brief model multilateral agreement on the recognition and enforcement of judgments. It then took several decades before, in 1965 a Convention on Choice of Court Agreements saw the light of the day and, in 1971, the Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil and Commercial Matters was first signed. These, and other Hague Conventions had a great impact on the 1968 Brussels Convention. The Jenard report is full of references to the 1971 Convention in particular.

So, was there to be a future for both instruments, the Brussels and the Hague judgments Convention? The instruments were perfectly compatible and could have happily coexisted. The reality was different, however. The European countries got fully absorbed in their enthusiasm for the Brussels Convention, and then its extension to the United Kingdom, Ireland, and Denmark, and as a result they lost interest in the Hague Convention. More generally, the common regulation of private international law relations with third countries was not a priority for Europe at the time: the focus was solely on European integration.

² See G Droz, *La compétence judiciaire et effets des jugements dans le marché commun* (Etude de la Convention de Bruxelles du 27 septembre 1968), Dalloz, Paris (1972), stressing the decisive role of integration into the European Community for the scope and structure of the Convention.

³ H Laufer, *La libre circulation des jugements dans une union judiciaire - Une idée géniale de T.M.C. Asser, visionnaire de la Convention de Bruxelles*, Peter Lang, Berne (1992).

Following the lifting of the Iron Curtain in 1989, globalization brought a new dynamic. The Centenary Session of the Hague Conference in 1993 adopted the *Convention on Protection of Children and Cooperation in respect of Intercountry Adoption* (Hague Adoption Convention), which succeeded in building a bridge between what we would now call the “global South” and the “global North”. In that same year, the HCCH began preparatory work on a “mixed convention” on civil and commercial judgements.⁴ The hope was that this would lead to an instrument of similar global importance as the Hague Children’s Conventions. However, the negotiations broke down, mainly on economic rivalry between Europe and the United States, centred on disagreement over the rules governing the jurisdiction of the courts.

The negotiations were further complicated by the Treaty of Amsterdam, concluded in 1997 and entered into force in 1999, which opened the door to a transfer of legislative powers in matters of private international law from the Member States to the European Union (EU). This could not leave indifferent an organization in which the European States have always played such an important role. In response, therefore, the Hague Conference developed a two-pronged strategy. First, it embarked on a rapid expansion of the organization with major countries such as Brazil, Russia, South Africa, and India, to strengthen the organization’s global reach. Secondly, it revised its Statute to allow the European Union to join the organization. In addition, consensus as a negotiating method was now formally introduced.

B. Emergence of a common principle of governance: global problems should preferably be dealt with at global level, regional problems at regional level

The years 2005-2007 marked a turning point. The EU joined the Hague Conference as a member alongside its Member States. This accession had a twofold effect. First, it profoundly altered the dynamic between the Union and its Member States within the HCCH, where the Union previously had only observer status, whereas it now became the spokesperson for the EU, coordinating the views of its Member States. Secondly, it created a new relationship with the other Member States of the Conference, third States from the EU’s point of view. Indeed, membership of the Conference has given the EU a global forum in which to act as a global player in the field of private international law.

⁴ “Some Reflections of the Permanent Bureau on a general convention on enforcement of judgments” (Prel. Doc. No 17 of May 1992, in Hague Conference on Private International Law, *Proceedings of the Seventeenth Session*, Tome I, First Part (1995), p. 231).

This new political and institutional configuration has laid the foundations for the emergence of *a common principle of governance*, gradually to be shared by the European Union, its Member States, and the Hague Conference. In simple terms, the principle is as follows: global private international law issues should preferably be dealt with at global level, regional issues at regional level, while some issues are best dealt with at national level.

This emerging principle resembles what Paul Beaumont has called “reverse subsidiarity”, “the idea that in areas of Union competence... the Union should not act internally if the objectives cannot be sufficiently achieved by Union legislation and can be better achieved by an international treaty”.⁵ The principle referred to here encompasses this idea but takes as its starting point the nature of the private international law issues - global, regional, national - and the level of governance best suited to deal with them - global, regional, national. There are ‘ifs’ and ‘buts’ to this principle, but we can recognise it in the evolution of events since the beginning of this century.

It took some time, however, before the principle became apparent. The fate of the *Convention on the law applicable to certain rights in respect of securities held with an intermediary* (adopted in 2002, signed in 2006) seemed to contradict this principle. Initially, the EU took an active part in the negotiations on this instrument. When the Convention was adopted, the European Commission proposed to sign it. But at that stage, signature was blocked by certain EU Member States. So, despite the entry into force of the Treaty for the United States, Switzerland and Mauritius, and the possibility of participating in a global arrangement, the EU is still stuck in a regional arrangement for what is undoubtedly a global issue arising in an eminently global financial market.

Yet this disappointing result seems rather the exception. During the subsequent negotiations at The Hague on the 2005 *Convention on Choice of Court Agreements*—the issue of choice of court, its conditions and its effects unquestionably being a global issue - the EU showed the way forward. It was the EU that brought the Convention into force in 2015. The negotiations also proved that solutions found at global level could lead to improvements at European level. In its 2003 *Gasser* judgment, the CJEU had stated that the Brussels I regulation required strict compliance with the *prior tempore potior*

⁵ P Beaumont, “International Family Law in Europe - The Maintenance Project, the Hague Conference and the EC: A Triumph of Reverse Subsidiarity” *Rebels Z* 2009, p.509. See also P Beaumont “Respecting Reverse Subsidiarity as an excellent strategy for the European Union at The Hague Conference on Private International Law - reflections in the context of the Judgments Project”. *Europejski Przegląd Sądowy*, 2016 (10), pp. 13-17. <http://www.czasopisma.wolterskluwer.pl/european-judiciary-review>

iure rule⁶. But this allowed a malicious party to get out from under the choice of forum and approach a court of its own choice, notably using the “Italian torpedo”. At the Hague, the negotiators rejected this approach and preferred respect for party autonomy over the *prior tempore* rule⁷. This rule in the Convention, in turn, paved the way for the adoption of a similar rule at the EU level when the Brussels I Regulation was recast in 2012.⁸

A second noteworthy point regarding the Brussels I recast is this. The EU would have been free to introduce in the recast a rule allowing the court of a Member State to decline jurisdiction in favour of a court of a *third* State not also bound by the Convention, if that third court had been chosen by the parties to an exclusive choice of court agreement but was seised *after* a court of the Union had been seised.⁹ However, Brussels I recast refrained from introducing such a rule. This self-limitation by the EU leaves more room for the Choice of Court Convention and thereby encourages third States to join this Convention.

After the Choice of Court Convention came the negotiations on the *Convention on the Recovery of Child Support and Other Forms of Family Maintenance* (Maintenance Convention) and its 2007 *Protocol on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations*. The recovery of child support, in particular, was recognized very early on as a global problem¹⁰, and it was up to the HCCH to find a solution adapted to current circumstances. But here one of the limitations of the common principle of governance became apparent.

It was clear from the outset of the negotiations that it would be impossible to reach global agreement on the rules of jurisdiction of the courts. The main reason was the requirement in United States law for a minimum of contacts between the defendant and the forum, which excludes the forum based solely on the habitual residence of the maintenance creditor, even though this is considered an essential forum by many other States. So, no (direct) rules on jurisdiction of the courts appear in the 2007 Convention.

Therefore, understandably, the EU decided to fill this gap, leading to *Regulation (EC) No 4/2009 of 18 December 2008 on jurisdiction, applicable law,*

⁶ CJEU C-116/02, 9 December 2003, *Gasser v. MISAT*, ECLI: EU :C:2003:65

⁷ Choice of Court Convention, Art 6

⁸ Brussels I Recast, Art 31

⁹ Choice of Court Convention, Art 26 (6) (a).

¹⁰ See the United Nations Convention on the Recovery Abroad of Maintenance of 1956 and the Hague Conventions on the Law Applicable to Maintenance Obligations towards Children of 1956 and on the Recognition and Enforcement of Decisions relating to Maintenance Obligations towards Children of 1958. These three instruments are replaced by the 2007 Maintenance Recovery Convention.

recognition and enforcement of decisions and cooperation in matters relating to maintenance obligations (Maintenance Regulation). However, first, the Regulation does not address the question of applicable law but refers to the 2007 Hague Protocol.¹¹

Secondly, the Regulation does not provide unilaterally for the recognition and enforcement by the EU Member States of maintenance decisions given in third countries not also bound by the 2007 Maintenance Convention. Again, this leaves room for the Maintenance Convention as an instrument of global governance and encourages third States to join the 2007 Treaty.

The 2019 *Convention on the Recognition and Enforcement of Foreign Judgments in Civil or Commercial Matters* (Judgments Convention) offers another example. Indeed, in a resolution on the revision of Brussels I adopted in 2010, the European Parliament had already explicitly stated the essence of the common governance principle. In its resolution, Parliament warned against giving the revised Regulation a reflexive effect because “*the problem is a global one* and the solution should therefore also be sought, in parallel, within the framework of the Hague Conference, through the resumption of negotiations on the Convention on International Judgments”. Parliament asked the Commission to try to “breathe new life into this project...” and, interestingly, urged “the Commission to study the question of the extent to which the 2007 Lugano Convention could serve as a model and inspiration for such a convention on international judgments”.¹²As we know, that did not happen, as the 2019 Convention does not deal with the original jurisdiction of the courts, but only with the effects of a foreign judgment.

The view that the multilateral Hague Conventions should provide the framework for cooperation in the field of private international law with third States, appears very clearly in the Commission’s Communication of 4 May 2021 to the Parliament and Council “Assessment on the application of the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland to accede to the 2007 Lugano Convention”:

“The Commission takes the view that the European Union should not give its consent to the accession of the United Kingdom to the 2007 Lugano Convention. For the European Union, the Lugano Convention is a flanking measure of the internal market and relates to the EU-EFTA/EEA context. In relation to all other third countries the consistent policy of the European

¹¹ Maintenance Regulation, Chapter III. Art. 15, with effect on the rules of Chapter IV on recognition and enforcement of decisions

¹² European Parliament report A7-0219/2010, par. 15, “Application of the Regulation within the international legal order”. Emphasis added.

Union is to promote cooperation within the framework of the multilateral Hague Conventions. The United Kingdom is a third country without a special link to the internal market. Therefore, there is no reason for the European Union to depart from its general approach in relation to the United Kingdom. Consequently, the Hague Conventions should provide the framework for future cooperation between the European Union and the United Kingdom in the field of civil judicial cooperation”¹³.

In its communication, the Commission announced its intention to propose EU conclusion of the 2019 Judgments Convention and suggested that the UK should do the same. Indeed, the EU joined the 2019 Convention on 29 August 2022, and the UK signed the Convention on 12 January 2024 with the intention to ratify the instrument before the end of the year.

The European Union – at the time still counting the UK among its members – played a leading role in the negotiations on the Judgments Convention. It was the first to accede to the Treaty, which entered into force on 1 September 2023 between the EU and Ukraine¹⁴.

More implicitly, the emerging common governance principle has manifested itself in *Council Regulation (EU) 2019/1111 of 25 June 2019 concerning jurisdiction and the recognition and enforcement of judgments in matrimonial matters and the matters of parental responsibility as well as international child abduction* (Brussels II ter Regulation).

The 2003 Brussels II bis Regulation had distanced itself from both the 1980 *Convention on the Civil Aspects of International Child Abduction* (Child Abduction Convention) and the 1996 *Convention on Jurisdiction, Applicable Law, Recognition, Enforcement and Co-operation in respect of Parental Responsibility and Measures for the Protection of Children* (1996 Convention). In particular, it strengthened the child return mechanism in relations between EU Member States and reduced the powers of the court of the Member State of refuge. The CJEU had strengthened this policy even further.

The Brussels II ter Regulation, on the other hand, represents a clear return to the worldwide sources, the 1980 and 1996 Conventions. The rigorous priority return mechanism, although not abolished, has been very much mitigated.¹⁵

¹³ Document (2021) 222 final, eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52021DC0222

¹⁴ On that same date Uruguay, as the first non-European State, deposited its instrument of ratification of the Convention.

¹⁵ See in particular Articles 29(3), (5) and (6), limiting the forced return mechanism to cases where the court of habitual residence is seised of an application for examination of the

Similarly, the Proposal of 31 May 2023 for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of measures and cooperation in respect of the protection of adults¹⁶ is explicitly intended to *supplement* the 2000 *Convention on the International Protection of Adults* (Protection of Adults Convention), and not to replace it with a European variant.¹⁷

C. Implementation of the principle: drafting aspects

The implementation of the emerging principle that private international law issues should preferably be dealt with at the corresponding level of governance has, for both the Hague Conference and the European Union, policy as well as drafting implications. First, a word about the drafting implications.

1. HCCH

For the Hague Conference, the principle implies that drafting should focus on global issues and provide ample opportunity for regional private international law cooperation. Except for the Hague Securities Convention, all Hague Conventions leave room for regional arrangements, both earlier and later, on the same subject matter in principle without limitation. However, there are two main exceptions to this rule.

First, as a condition for any regional deviation from its rules, the Convention may require a certain degree of integration within the region. Thus, the 1996 Convention allows Contracting States to adopt different rules, but only in respect of children habitually resident in those States, and provided that they do not affect their obligations to third Contracting States.¹⁸ A similar rule is found in the Protection of Adults Convention.¹⁹

The second exception is that, where Hague Conventions implement global human rights standards, divergent regional agreements cannot devi-

merits of custody rights (and not before, as the CJEU decided in its judgment in Case C-211/10 PPU (*Povse*)), and above all Article 56(4) to (6), which reopens the possibility of exceptionally invoking the ground for refusal in Article 13(1)(b) of the Child Abduction Convention at the stage of enforcement of a decision by the court of the Member State of origin.

¹⁶ https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:28ff9588-007b-11ee-87ec-01aa75ed71a1.0010.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

¹⁷ See recitals 7-8, 18-23 and 64 of the proposal for a Regulation. It is even proposed that the text of the Convention be attached to the Regulation, see Art. 4, see also Articles 5-8, 27, 59 and 65-66.

¹⁸ Article 52(2)

¹⁹ Article 49(2)

ate from these standards. The Child Abduction Convention allows Contracting States to derogate from the Convention to limit, but not relax, restrictions on the return of children.²⁰ This Convention thus reinforces the rule on the non-return of abducted children contained in article 11 of the *United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child* (CRC). Similarly, the Adoption Convention only authorizes post-Convention arrangements between Contracting States aimed at improving the application of the Convention in their mutual relations and only authorizes derogations from its procedural rules, not its substantive rules.²¹ The Convention thus gives concrete form to and reinforces Article 21 of the CRC.

On the other hand, existing regional arrangements may set limits to the drafting of global instruments. The 2015 Principles on Choice of Law in Commercial Contracts illustrate this point. The question of the law applicable to contractual obligations is a global issue. However, the pre-existence of *Regulation (EC) No 593/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 on the law applicable to contractual obligations* (Rome I) and the 1994 *Inter-American Convention on the Law Applicable to International Contracts*²², both of which also allow the parties to choose the applicable law, prevented the conclusion of a binding global instrument containing universally applicable conflict of laws rules: “unification universelle sur unification universelle ne vaut”²³. The Principles therefore took the form of a non-binding instrument.

2. EU

For the European Union, developing the principle of governance according to the nature of the problem will mean: focusing on issues of particular interest to the Union’s economies and societies and, where global instruments already exist, implementing or supplementing those instruments. Conflicts with global treaties must be avoided and the limits that the global instrument may set to regional unification must be respected.

Thus, both the Brussels II ter Regulation and the Maintenance Obligations Regulation do not deal with applicable law but refer to the global Hague instruments in this area.²⁴ In addition, Brussels II ter introduces new, more precise provisions to clarify its application in relation to the Child Abduction

²⁰ Article 36

²¹ Article 39(1)

²² The Convention only entered into force between Venezuela and Mexico.

²³ “Universal unification upon universal unification does not work”, G Droz, “Regards sur le droit international privé comparé”, *Recueil des cours*, t 229. 1991 IV, p. 390.

²⁴ However, whereas the Regulation on maintenance obligations contains an explicit provision to this effect, see note 11, the Brussels I ter Regulation only sets it out in a recital (92).

Convention and the 1996 Convention.²⁵ The Commission's recent proposal for the protection of adults is very clearly grafted onto the Protection of Adults Convention, which is even attached to the proposed Regulation.

As regards the other existing Hague Conventions, the EU instruments respect their continued application by the EU Member States that are party to them but block the possibility of future ratifications. This is sometimes questionable. For example, *Regulation (EU) No 650/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of decisions and the acceptance and enforcement of authentic instruments in matters of succession and the creation of a European Certificate of Succession* might well have encouraged those EU Member States that are not yet party to the widely ratified 1961 *Convention on the Conflict of Laws Relating to the Form of Testamentary Dispositions* to accede to that Convention rather than provide for its own rule.²⁶

D. Implementation of the principle: policy aspects

If we look to the future, what would be the *policy* implications of this principle of governance at the appropriate level - global, regional, national - for private international law issues - global, regional, national? Of course, these levels of governance are not static: some problems of private international law first arise at national level, and then take on a regional dimension. And those that initially arise at regional level will tend to become global.

From this perspective, which global issues require global regulation of private international law, and which regional problems rather require a regional approach?

1. HCCH

First a word about global issues. It has rightly been observed in relation to the Judgments Convention that it "falls within a framework in which human rights and the objectives of sustainable development constitute an important normative element of international law".²⁷ Indeed, this comment applies more generally to the Hague Conventions, for some even more obviously than to the Judgments Convention. It also provides guidance for the future work of the HCCH, because by aligning with this framework, the Con-

²⁵ Arts. 96 and 97, respectively.

²⁶ Art. 27; cf. art 75 (1).

²⁷ M. Dotta, "Grounds for Refusal", in M. Weller et al, *The HCCH 2019 Judgments Convention*, Hart (2023), pp.71-85 (p.71).

ference will find global norms and values that its work can, and often should, serve.

As far as human rights are concerned, the *Resolution on Human Rights and Private International Law* adopted by the Institute of International Law in 2021²⁸ is an important reminder that these two branches of law are not separate silos but complement each other.

This can be seen most clearly in the interaction between the Hague Conventions on the international protection of children and the UN Convention on the Rights of the Child. This multilateral UN treaty, which has been almost universally ratified, identifies a series of cross-border legal problems, many of which give rise to issues of private international law which call for solutions at the global level. This is precisely what, among others, the 1980, 1993, 1996 and 2007 Hague Conventions offer²⁹.

Less noticed but nonetheless important: the Hague Conventions on civil procedure - those of 1965 on the service of documents abroad, of 1970 on the taking of evidence abroad, of 1980 on international access to justice, the Choice of Court Convention of 2005, and the Judgments Convention of 2019 - can all be linked to Article 14(1) of the 1966 UN *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*. Although this provision does not explicitly refer to cross-border situations, there is no doubt that it applies to such cases. The European Court of Human Rights has confirmed this for the comparable Article 6 of the European Convention on Human Rights.³⁰ These Hague Conventions help to ensure that borders do not impede access to justice across the vast field of civil and commercial law.

A similar point applies to Article 23 of this Covenant concerning the right to marry and found a family of 1966³¹ and the comparable provisions of the European (art. 12), American (art. 17) and African (art. 18) Human Rights Conventions. Once again, whilst these articles do not address in so many words the application of this right beyond national borders, it is inconceivable that they would not apply to such situations.

²⁸ https://www.idi-iil.org/app/uploads/2023/09/2023_150-DECLARATION-EN.pdf, Rapporteur F Pocar.

²⁹ See articles 9-11 and 35 (1980 and 1996 Conventions), 22 (1996 Convention), 20-22 (1993 Convention) and 27 (2007 Convention). Recital 9 of the Second Optional Protocol to the CRC on the sale of children, child prostitution and child pornography refers to the 1980, 1993 and 1996 Conventions.

³⁰ ECHR, 13 October 2009, *Selin Aslı Öztürk v. Turkey*, §§ 39-41: any person having a legal interest in the recognition of a judgment given abroad must be able to apply for it (concerning the recognition of a divorce judgment given abroad).

³¹ Supplemented by art. 10(1) of the UN *International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights*.

Questions of private international law relating to the recognition of a foreign marriage or divorce (non-recognition of a divorce may stand in the way of a new marriage!), as well as their effects in terms of property and inheritance, abound throughout the world. These are problems already addressed by several Hague Conventions, but to date with limited success in terms of ratifications. Interestingly, however, the European Union has used the *Convention on the Recognition of Divorces and Legal Separations* (1970), the *Convention on the Law Applicable to Matrimonial Property Regimes* (1978), and the *Convention on the Law Applicable to Succession to the Estates of Deceased Persons* (1989) as models for the European regulations in these areas.³²

Since these are all global PIL issues, which become more pressing with increased worldwide mobility of persons and families, the Hague Conference might well consider in turn to use these EU Regulations as stepping stones for renewed efforts to address these issues at the global level.

Private international law also plays a role in the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).³³ In fact, in cross-border situations, the Hague Conventions contribute, or have the potential to contribute, to SDG 16.3: *Promoting the rule of law at the national and international levels and ensuring equal access to justice for all*.

The preamble to the Judgments Convention contains, perhaps, an implicit reference to the UN Agenda 2030 where the Contracting Parties express their willingness “to promote effective access to justice for all and to facilitate, at the multilateral level, rules-based trade and investment, as well as mobility, through judicial cooperation”. This corresponds not only to SDG 16.3, but also to SDG 17.10: “Promote a universal multilateral trading system”³⁴, and 10.7: *Facilitate...mobility...* However, the explanatory report to the Convention makes no explicit reference to the 2030 Agenda, or to the UN Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights, or to the many UN instruments on the environment and climate change. This does not mean that the Convention does not serve the objectives of these instruments.³⁵ However, it does suggest that awareness of the importance of private international law

³² Namely, the Brussels II Regulation, *Council Regulation (EU) 2016/1103 of 24 June 2016 implementing enhanced cooperation in the area of jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition and enforcement of judgments in matrimonial property regimes and the 2012 Succession Regulation*, above C.

³³ See R Michaels V Ruiz-Abou-Nigm and H van Loon, *The Private Side of Transforming our World - UN Sustainable Development Goals 2030 and the Role of Private International Law*, Intersentia, Cambridge, 2021.

³⁴ See also SDGs 2a, 7a and 10b.

³⁵ See *The Private Side...* (n.33), passim.

in achieving the SDGs and, more generally, the global framework referred to above, is still in its infancy.

Because of its very restricted indirect jurisdiction ground for tort matters³⁶, the Judgments Convention will have a limited effect on the recognition and enforcement of foreign judgments relating to environmental damage and climate change. The 2030 Agenda calls for urgent action to combat pollution³⁷, climate change³⁸ and biodiversity loss³⁹. The United Nations General Assembly Resolution of 28 July 2022, *The human right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment*⁴⁰, affirms this call. All this strengthens the case for a global private international law instrument on environmental issues, including climate change. Considerable preparatory work has already been done, and the rules developed by the EU in this area could also inspire such a project.⁴¹

2. EU

Let us now look at regional issues. What regional PIL issues stand out which the EU should or could address. First, as we have already seen, we must admit that it is not possible to solve all problems of private international law of a global nature at the global level. In such cases, a solution must be found at the regional level.

In this context, however, the *Proposal for a Council Regulation on jurisdiction, applicable law, recognition of decisions and acceptance of authentic instruments in matters of parentage and the creation of a European parentage certificate*⁴² raises questions. The challenges of private international law on parentage are an intrinsically global problem. It is true that no global regime is yet in force in this area. But the Hague Conference is working on this, and it would be wise to await the completion of this global work before the EU begins its own work on the subject. At the very least, the Union's work should be very carefully coordinated with that of The Hague.

³⁶ Art. 5 (1) (j) A judgment shall be entitled to recognition and enforcement if...the judgment relates to a non-contractual obligation arising out of death, personal injury, damage to or loss of tangible property and the act or omission directly causing the damage was committed in the State of origin, irrespective of where the damage occurred.

³⁷ SDGs 3.9, 6.3, and 14.1

³⁸ SDG 13

³⁹ SDG 14

⁴⁰ Resolution A/Res/76/300, [A_RES_76_300-EN - PDF](#)

⁴¹ See our study "Principles and Building Blocks for a Global Legal Framework for Civil Litigation in Environmental Matters" in *Uniform Law Review*, 23 (2), 2018, pp. 298-318.

⁴² *Com (2022) 694 final*, of 7 December 2022

An example where regional rules of private international law are desirable but not currently envisaged is provided by the Commission's Proposal for a *Directive on the duty of care of companies with regard to sustainable development*.⁴³ This is an area where the EU has shown leadership and where it could go further than is possible at global level. However, as GEDIP has pointed out, the absence of private international law rules weakens the proposal. For example, the proposed directive also applies to non-EU companies with a turnover in the EU, but it does not offer the possibility of bringing an action against such a company before the court of a Member State, potentially resulting in an uneven level playing field.⁴⁴

There are at least two other major areas of potential activity for the EU in private international law. One is the question of jurisdiction of EU Member States' courts over persons domiciled in third countries, which is currently left to the national systems of the Member States. The other is the codification of the general part of private international law at Union level. These two issues are, as such, also relevant at global level. All countries face the question of how far the jurisdiction of their courts extends in relation to foreign-based companies and persons. However, the outcome of negotiations on the HCCH judgment project suggests that a global agreement on direct grounds of jurisdiction is currently out of reach. There are therefore good reasons to try to harmonize these rules within the EU framework, with the exception of exclusive choice of court agreements, which should be left to the Choice of Court Convention. As for the codification of the general part of private international law, this would ideally be a task for the HCCH, but this is not currently feasible, however, given its more advanced stage of PIL codification and more limited number of members, the EU might wish to start developing such a general part, benefiting from the results of GEDIP's current work in this area.

E. Conclusion

The work of both the HCCH and the EU on private international law has its common origin in the efforts of the pioneers of the nineteenth century, foremost among whom were Mancini and Asser. The Hague Confer-

⁴³ Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on corporate sustainability due diligence and amending Directive (EU) 2019/1937 of 23 February 2022.

⁴⁴ Recommendation of the European Group for Private International Law/ Groupe européen de droit international privé on the proposal for a Directive of 23 February 2022 on corporate sustainability due diligence, Recommendation-GEDIP2022E.pdf (gedip-egpil.eu), following its Recommendation to the Commission of 8 October 2021 Recommendation-GEDIP-Recommendation-EGPIL-final-1.pdf (gedip-egpil.eu).

ences, later the international organization The Hague Conference, began largely as a project of European countries on European legal systems, and remained so for a long time. The development of the HCCH into a global organization was stimulated by the Treaty of Amsterdam, which enabled legislative activities by the EU in the field of private international law. This in turn led to the Hague Conference accelerating the expansion of its global reach and allowing the EU to join the organization. The EU has thus emerged as a global player within the framework of the HCCH, which has become the privileged forum for the EU to negotiate its private international law relations with third States. This has given the EU a global perspective that it might not have gained otherwise.

We are thus witnessing a development whereby the EU is cooperating within the HCCH with third countries in an attempt to resolve global problems. As a result, with a few exceptions, it only acts internally to solve such problems if this objective cannot be achieved at global level. This has implications for the drafting of Hague and EU instruments. The Hague instruments should leave room for regional codification, which is indeed the case. Conversely, EU instruments should preferably deal with issues of particular interest to the EU. This requires the HCCH and the EU to think in terms of governance policy about the best level, global or regional, at which issues existing or arising at each level, global or regional, can be addressed.

According to the Declaration adopted on 2 September 2023 by the Institute of International Law on its 150th anniversary, “the moral, legal, economic and other challenges of our times are increasingly taking planetary dimensions”.⁴⁵ It would undoubtedly be desirable for the EU and the HCCH to explore together, with other interested parties, what should be the role of private international law in responding to major global problems such as environmental degradation, climate change and the loss of biodiversity. It would undoubtedly be desirable for the EU and the HCCH, together with other interested parties, to explore and consider together what role unification of private international law should play in addressing major global issues such as cross-border pollution, climate change and biodiversity loss.

⁴⁵ See above, fn28